

IDENTIFICATION GUIDE TO THE SPIDERS OF THE SOUTPANSBERG TRANSEK

Compiled by A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman

1. AGELENIDAE

BASED ON LEON LOTZ there are the following 4 spp.

Agelena sp. 5 n. sp.

Distribution in South Africa: Limpopo: Lajuma (-23.03, 29.45).

Benoitia sp. 2 [possibly *B. (Agelena) australis*, or *B. deserticola* or *rhodesia*.]
 Klein Kariba (-24.83, 28.33); Lajuma (-23.03, 29.45); Mosdene (-24.52, 28.70); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Game Reserve (-23.97, 29.47); Roedtan (-24.59, 29.09).

AGELENIDAE

- **association:** funnel-web
- **body size:** 510 mm
- **three claws**
- **eight eyes in two rows**
- **posterior spinnerets two-segmented, long and slender, with apical segment tapering towards tip**

Agelena australis (Simon, 1896)

Agelena sp. 5

Benoitia rhodesia

Maimuna deserticola (Simon, 1910)

Mistaria leucopyga (Pavesi, 1883)

Olorunia punctata Lehtinen, 1967

Benoitia sp. 2 new

Benoitia sp. 4 new

Benoitia sp. 7 new

AGELENIDAE cont.

***Benoitia* sp. 4 [possibly *B. australis*, *deserticola* or *rhodesia*.]**

Limpopo: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.13); Dendron (-23.26, 29.48); Kruger National Park, N. of S52 crossing Shingwezi River (-23.17, 31.30); Lajuma (-23.03, 29.45); Pafuri (Walers Camp) (-22.42, 30.91); Rochdale, N. slopes of Soutpansberg (-22.90, 29.68); Stoke (-22.48, 29.88)

***Benoitia* sp. 7**

***Benoitia* sp. 7**

Distribution in South Africa: Limpopo: Lajuma (-23.03, 29.45).

Habitat (biomes): SB. **Protected areas***

Known distribution: South Africa.

Conservation status: *endemicity*: 6, *abundance*: 1 [?].

Taxonomic status: 1.

2. AMAUROBIIDAE

AMAUROBIIDAE

- association: retreat-web
- body size: 2–5 mm
- three claws
- six or eight eyes in two rows
- carapace longer than wide, narrower in eye region
- some genera with cribellum

SPECIES LAJUMA

Chresiona invalida (Simon, 1898)

Pseudauximus annulatus Purcell, 1908

2345dm Altitudinal, Spiders, Miturgidae

2557d Altitudinal, Spiders, Miturgidae

KEY TO THE GENERA

1. Cribellum present 2
 - Cribellum absent..... *Chresiona*
2. AME smaller than PME..... *Obatala*
 - AME larger or same size as PME; AER usually strongly procurved.. 3
3. Embolus spiral lamella with loop, originates apically; epigynum with central septum, bilobate *Macrobanus*
 - Embolus arched lamella distally modified originates apical to subapical; epigynum small triangular plate *Pseudauximus*

Pseudauximus sp.

Chresiona sp.

3. AMMOXENIDAE

AMMOXENIDAE

- *association*: sand divers, usually found in sandy areas near termite nests
- body size: 1.5–8 mm
- two claws, tarsi pseudosegmented (*Ammoxenus*)
- eight-eyed spiders
- chelicerae modified for burrowing, with strong setae (*Ammoxenus*) or digging scoop (*Rastellus*)
- median spinnerets set slightly forward

AMMOXENIDAE

Ammoxenus psammodromus Simon, 1910

Rastellus kariba

Rastellus kariba

Ammoxenus psammodromus Simon, 1910

4. ANAPIDAE

Crozetulus rhodesiensis Brignoli, 1981

5. ARANEIDAE

Acanthepeira'-like

Araneus apricus

Araneus legonensis

Araneus nigroquadratus

Araneus strupifera

Arsneus sp. 2
Soos neoscona

Araneidae sp. 4

Araneidae sp. 1 - *Ursa turbinata*

Araneidae 8
Soos Hypsosinga room 6 swart
kollie

Araneidae sp. 2

Araneidae 10

Araneidae sp. 3

Argiope australis

Argiope lobata

Cyclosa insulana

Cyphalonatus larvatus

Caerostris sexcuspidata

Cyrtophora citricola

Gasteracantha

Chorizopes sp.

Hypsosinga lithyphantoides

Hypsosinga sp. 2

Eriovixia

Ideocaira sp. 1

Nemoscclus elongates /Cyclosa

Lipocrea longissima

Nemoscclus sp. 3

Nemoscclus tubicola

2297d Altitudinal, Araneidae, 03_12N,
Spiders, sp 02

Prasonica seriata

Nemoscclus cotti

2309lpv Altitudinal, Spiders

Singa lawrencei

Neoscona blondeli

Neoscona subfusca

Neoscona penicillipes

Neoscona triangular

Neoscona quincasea

Pararaneus spectator

Neoscona penicillipes (Karsch, 1879)

Neoscona novella (Simon, 1901)

Neoscona rapta (Thorell, 1899)

Mahemba hewitti (Lessert, 1930)

6. BARYPHELIDAE

Pisenor notius Simon, 1889

FIRST MALE?

7. CAPONIIDAE

CAPONIIDAE

- *association*: usually found in drier, more arid grasslands
- *body size*: 6–13 mm
- three claws
- two- or eight-eyed spiders
- orange colour
- booklungs replaced by two pairs of tracheae
- spinnerets modified, with median spinnerets situated between anterior spinnerets

Caponia chelifera

CHEIRACANTHIIDAE

MITURGIDAE

- association: free-living on vegetation
- body size: 4–12 mm
- two claws, front legs longer than others
- eight eyes in two rows
- usually creamy-yellow with dark face
- resemble Clubionidae but front legs longer

Cheiracanthium angolensis

MITURGIDAE

- Cheiracanthium aculeutum*
- Cheiracanthium africanum* Lessert, 1921
- Cheiracanthium angolensis* Lotz, 2007
- Cheiracanthium furculatum* Karsch, 1879
- Cheiracanthium vansoni* Lawrence, 1936
- Cheiramiona clavigera* (Simon, 1897)
- Cheiramiona krugerensis* Lotz, 2002

Cheiracanthium furculatum

Cheiracanthium aculeutum

Cheiracanthium africanum

Cheiracanthium vansoni

8. CLUBIONIDAE

CLUBIONIDAE

- association: free-living on grass and foliage
- body size: 3–15 mm
- two claws, front legs shorter than leg IV
- eight eyes in two rows
- usually cream with dark face

Clubiona abbajensis Strand, 1906

Clubiona bevisi

Clubiona godfreyi

Clubiona lawrencei

Clubiona pupillaris

Clubiona godfreyi

Clubiona

Clubiona pupillaris

Clubiona abbajensis

Clubiona bevisi

Clubiona pongolensis

9. CYATHOLIPIDAE

CYATHOLIPIDAE

- *association*: orb-webs in grass and foliage
- body size: 2–4 mm
- three claws; legs very slender, sometimes very long, leg I longest
- eight eyes in two rows, lateral eyes sometimes on small tubercles
- abdomen cylindrical, oval or triangular
- spiracles linked externally to transverse grooves

Cyatholipus sp. 2

Cyatholipus isolatus Griswold, 1987

10. CORINNIDAE

Brachyphae sp. 1	1
Cambalida coriacea Simon, 1909	1
Castianeira fulvipes Simon, 1896	1
Cetonana simoni (Lawrence, 1942)	1
Copa flavoplumosa Simon, 1885	1
Corinna natalensis	1
Corinnomma lawrencei Haddad 2006	1
Corinnomma radiata Haddad 2006	1
Graptartia tropicalis Haddad, 2004	1
Hortipes contubernalis Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000	1
Merenius simoni Lessert, 1921	1
Orthobula radiata Simon, 1897	1
Poachelas sp.	1
Pronophaea natalica Simon, 1897	1
Thysanina transversa Lyle & Haddad, 2006	1
Trachelas scopulifer Simon, 1896	1

Afroceto martini

Cambalida coriacea

Castianeira fulvipes

Corinna natalensis

CORINNIDAE

- association: usually found in humus rich areas and open grasslands
- body size: 2–12 mm
- two claws
- eight-eyed spiders
- colour highly variable, abdomen usually with markings
- some species with lycosiform colouration or ant- or velvet-ant mimics
- legs strongly spined, Trachelinae with ventral cusps on anterior legs, at least in

Taken from atlas

Apochinomma

Copa flavoplumosa

10. CORINNIDAE & TRACHELIDAE

Corinnomma lawrencei

Graptartia tropicalis

Corinnomma semiglabrum

Hortipes contubernalis

Fuchiba aquilonia

Orthobula radiata

Pronophaea natalica

Thysanina transversa

Vendaphaea lajuma

Trachelas scopulifer

Fuchibotulus kigelia

11. CTENIDAE

CTENIDAE

- *association*: usually found in humus rich areas
- body size: 15–20 mm
- two claws
- eight-eyed spiders
- resemble wolf spiders but eyes arranged differently (2:4:2)
- trochanters deeply notched

CTENIDAE

Ctenus gulosus

Ctenus transvaalensis Benoit, 1981

Ctenus gulosus

Ctenus transvaalensis

12. CYRTAUCHENIIDAE

CYRTAUCHENIIDAE

- size: 9–32 mm; sexual dimorphism in size and shape
- rastellum present
- female carapace glabrous; cephalic region strongly arched
- fovea broad, procurved
- chelicerae slender
- live in silk-lined burrows, the shape of which varies from single burrows, to Y-shaped, to the shape of a curved pipe; burrows close with wafer-like trapdoor

Key to the Genera of the Savanna Biome

1. Cheliceral furrow with one row of strong teeth in outer row (a), inner row with small denticles; apical segment of posterior spinnerets digitiform *Ancylotrypa*
 – Chelicerae with two rows of strong teeth (b); apical segment of posterior spinnerets short and dome-shaped *Homostola*

Homostola pardalina

2760p Altitudinal Spiders, 05_17N, Cyrtauchenidae, sp.02

2760d Altitudinal Spiders, 05_17N, Cyrtauchenidae, sp.02

Ancylotrypa brevipalpis

2428c Altitudinal Spiders

Ancylotrypa nuda

Ancylotrypa elongata Purcell,

13. DEINOPIDAE

DEINOPIDAE

- *association*: cribellate reduced orb-webs in grass and low foliage, sometimes modified
- body size: 6–25 mm
- three claws; anterior legs greatly elongated to hold net-like cribellate web
- eight eyes in two rows, lateral eyes on tubercles; posterior median eyes greatly enlarged
- cribellum and calamistrum present

Deinopis cornigera Gerstäcker, 1873

Menneus camelus Pocock, 1902

Deinopis cornigera

Menneus camelus

14. DICTYNIDAE

DICTYNIDAE

- *association*: small retreat-webs in grass and foliage
- body size: 1.5–5 mm
- three claws
- eight small eyes in two rows
- cribellum and calamistrum present
- Abdomen usually cream with dark markings

DICTYNIDAE

Archaeodictyna sp.01

Devade sp. 1

Mashimo leleupi Lehtinen, 1967

Archaeodictyna sp.01

Mashimo leleupi

15. DIPLURIDAE= EUAGRIDAE

DIPLURIDAE

- *association*: funnel-web
- *body size*: 16–22 mm, males more slender
- three claws
- eight eyes on tubercle
- posterior spinnerets very long, widely spaced

DIPLURIDAE

Allothele malawi Coyle, 1984

16. ERESIDAE

ERESIDAE

- *association*: retreat-web
- body size: 10–25 mm
- three claws
- eight eyes in two rows
- cribellum present
- carapace broad, males sometimes with hornlike structures on anterior edge of carapace
- body densely covered in short setae

Dresserus colsoni Tucker, 1920

Paradonea presleyi Miller, Griswold, Scharff, Rezac, Szuts & Marhabaie, 2012

Paradonea sp. BAIE WITH HARE

Seothyra fasciata

Stegodyphus africanus (Blackwall, 1866)

Seothyra fasciata

Paradonea parva

Stegodyphus africanus

Paradonea presleyi

EUTICHURIIDAE CONT

Cheiramiona lajuma Lotz, 2003

Cheiramiona

Cheiramiona clavigera

***Lessertina mutica* Lawrence, 1942**

Cheiramiona krugerensis

17. GNAPHOSIDAE

GNAPHOSIDAE

Aneplasa interrogationis Tucker, 1923

Aphantaulax inornata Tucker, 1923

Asemesthes ceresicola

Asemesthes corrugatus

Asemesthes lineatus

Asemesthes pallidus Purcell, 1908

Asemesthes paynteri Tucker, 1923

Asemesthes numisma Tucker, 1923

Asemesthes reflexus

Camillina arida (Purcell, 1907)

Camillina cordifera (Tullgren, 1910)

Drassodes solitarius Purcell, 1907

Echemus erutus Tucker, 1923

Ibala arcus Tucker, 1923

Ibala bilinearis

Megamyrmekion transvaalense Tucker, 1923

Pterotrichia auris (Tucker, 1923)

Pterotrichia varia (Tucker, 1923)

Scotophaeus sp. 1

Setaphis subtilis (Simon, 1897)

Trachyzelotes jaxartensis (Kronenberg, 1875)

Trephopoda sp. new?

Xerophaeus aurariarum Purcell, 1907

Xerophaeus bicavus Tucker, 1923

Zelotes caldarius (Purcell, 1907)

Zelotes corrugatus (Purcell, 1907)

Zelotes fuliginus (Purcell, 1907)

Zelotes hewitti Tucker, 1923

Zelotes natalensis Tucker, 1923

Zelotes otavi Fitzpatrick, 2007

Zelotes sclateri Tucker, 1923

Zelotes scrutatus

Zelotes tuckeri Roewer, 1951

Zelotes ungula

Aneplasa interrogationis

Aphantaulax inornata

Asemesthes ceresicola

Carapace yellowish brown, dark-edged abdomen with median serrated band and lateral infuscations. sternum with infuscated border.

Asemesthes ceresicola

Asemesthes lineatus

Asemesthes paynteri

Asemesthes numis-

Asemesthes reflexus

Asemesthes pallidus

Asemesthes purcelli

Ibala arcus

Ibala bilinearis

Asemesthes lineatus

Colour pale-yellow, the markings as in *A. pallidus* n. sp., except that the underside is entirely without black (except sometimes between the lung-opercula) and the legs are less strongly banded, the femora often with scarcely any infusate markings.

Asemesthes pallidus

General colour pale yellow .legs only slightly infusate .abdomen with medio-dorsal and 2 lateral dark bands

Asemesthes paynteri

Colour yellowish brown, carapace dark-edged, slightly mottled black..bdomen without pattern

Asemesthes numisma

Asemesthes reflexus

Asemesthes purcelli Tucker, 1923

Asemesthes purcelli

Camillina pavesii (

Camillina arida

Camillina cordifera

Drassodes bechuanicus Tucker, 1923

Drassodes solitarius

Drassodes helenae Purcell,

Ibala arcus

Superior border of ohelicera, with more than 3 teeth

"Setophis" arcus ♂

Echemus erutus

Ibala bilinearis

DARK KEGS
SMALL

Leptodrassex sp. 1

Gnaphosidae sp. 1
Small pale
Ame large
Prow slightly procurved

Superior border of chelicera with 3 or less teeth,*Ibala bilinearis*

2833

Ibala sp. 1 = kleiner geen groot
MA VENTRAAL GROOT
WIT; DORSAAL BANDE
LOOP AANEEN

Megamyrmeleon transvaalense

Setaphis subtilis

Trehopoda sp.

Pterotrichia auris

Trachyzelotes jaxartensis

Scotophaeus sp. 1

Xerophaeus aurariarum

Xerophaeus bicavus

Pterotrichia varia

Zelotes caldarius

Zelotes aridus

Zelotes corrugatus

Zelotes otavi

Zelotes fuliginus

Zelotes sclateri

Zelotes humilis

Zelotes scrutatus

Zelotes tuckeri

Zelotes natalensis =SEN SYN UNGULA

Zelotes haplodrassoides

Zelotes caldarius

Zelotes aridus

Zelotes corrugatus

Zelotes otavi

Zelotes fuliginus

Zelotes sclateri

Zelotes humilis

Zelotes scrutatus

Zelotes haplodrassoides

Zelotes tuckeri

Zelotes namaquus FitzPatrick,

Zelotes thick pointed embolis

Zelotes natalensis =SEN SYN UNGULA

NOW GNAPHOSIDAE

PRODIDOMIDAE

- Austrodomus* sp. 1
- Prodidomus capensis* Purcell, 1904
- Theuma elucubata* Tucker, 1923
- Theuma purcelli* Tucker, 1923

Austrodomus

- 1. Eyes in a circular arrangement; AER straight; PER strongly procurved; chelicerae diverging; fangs long and slender
.....Prodidominae

Austrodomus
Prodidomus

Prodidomus capensis

- Eyes not in circular arrangement; PER slightly recurved; chelicerae not diverging; fangs moderate length

.....Anagraphinae

Theuma

Theuma fusca Purcell, 1907 cara 4.1

Theuma elucubata 8.5 mm

Theuma purcelli 6mm

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18. HAHNIIDAE

HAHNIIDAE

- *association*: sheet-web
- body size: 2–6 mm
- three claws
- eight eyes in two rows
- spinnerets in a single row
-

HAHNIIDAE

Hahnia tabulicola Simon, 1898

Hahnia tabulicola

19. HERSILIIDAE

HERSILIIDAE

- *association*: free-living on bark
- body size: 7–10 mm
- two claws, third legs very short
- eight eyes grouped together on eye tubercle
- posterior spinnerets two-segmented, long and slender, with apical segment tapering towards tip

Hersilia sericea

HERSILIIDAE

Hersilia sericea Pocock, 1898

Tyrotama soutpansbergensis-Hersillidae

20. IDIOPIDAE

IDIOPIDAE

- size: 8–33 mm; sexual dimorphism in size and shape
- rastellum present
- eight eyes, with anterior lateral eyes close together on clypeal edge
- cephalic region arched and fovea procurved
- abdomen oval, except in *Galeosoma*
- sexual dimorphism in size and shape is very distinct; carapace more flattened in males
- live in silk-lined burrows of variable shape; burrows usually close with a wafer-like trapdoor

IDIOPIDAE

Ctenolopus sp. 1

Idiops castaneus Hewitt, 1913

KEY TO THE GENERA OF GAUTENG OF THE IDIOPINAE

(adapted from Griswold, 1984 and Raven, 1985)

1. Abdomen truncated, with apical part of domed with chitinized shield in females; soft bodied in males ***Galeosoma***
 - Abdomen soft-skinned, evenly rounded **2**
2. Sternum with 3 pairs of sigilla **3**
 - Sternum with 2 pairs of sigilla **4**
3. Posterior sigilla on sternum enlarged ***Gorgyrella***
 - Posterior sigilla on sternum small ***Segregara***
4. Row of strong cheliceral teeth on inner row, teeth in outer row reduce or only few small denticles present ***Ctenolophus***
 - Cheliceral furrow with two rows of equal strong teeth..... ***Idiops***

Ctenolophus fenoulheti

Female 8 mm. Carapace and legs chestnut brown; anterior legs almost black; femur IV dark above, lower surface and more distal parts of legs pale brown; abdomen fuscous (dark brownish-gray color)

Idiops castaneus

21. LINYPHIIDAE

LINYPHIIDAE

- *association*: sheet-web on grass and foliage
- body size: 1–5 mm
- three claws
- eight eyes in two rows, in some males eyes on tubercles or protuberances
- labium rebordered
- legs slender, with strong setae, on tibiae and metatarsi

LINYPHIIDAE

Meioneta natalensis Jocqué, 1984

Metaleptyphantes perexiguus (Simon & Fage, 1922)

Mecynidis sp

Microlinyphia sterilis (Pavesi, 1883)

Neriene natalensis Van Helsdingen, 1970

Pelecopsis sp. possible new

Metaleptyphantes perexiguus

Agyneta habra (Locket, 1968)

Microlinyphia sterilis

Pelecopsis janus

Mecynidis dentipalpis

=Araneidae sp. 4, 5,6

Neriene sp.

Neriene natalensis

Meioneta natalensis

22. LIOCRANIDAE

LIOCRANIDAE

- *association*: found under stones
- body size: 6–15 mm
- two claws
- eight eyes in two rows (4:4)
- tibiae and metatarsi I and II armed below with paired rows of many long spines with distinct bases
- median spinnerets of females usually medially flattened

Rhaeboctesis exilis

Rhaeboctesis trinotatus Tucker, 1920

Rhaeboctesis exilis

Rhaeboctesis trinotatus

Rhaeboctesis

23. LYCOSIDAE

Stefan no 2987
Lycosidae sp. 14

Allocosa testacea Roewer,

Allocosa excerta

Allocosa tuberculipalpa

Allocosa lawrencei

Allocosa umtalica (Purcell, 1903)

Evippomma squamulatum

Minicosa neptuna

Hippasa elienae

Pardosa crassipalpis

Hogna spenceri (Pocock, 1898)

Pardosa leipoldti

Ocyale guttata

Pterartoria fissivittata Purcell, 1903

Pardosa enucleata Roewer, 1959

Allocosa excerta

Proevippa albiventris (

Proevippa fascicularis

Proevippa biampliata

Proevippa schreineri (Purcell, 1903)

Proevippa wanlessi

Trabea heteroculata

Trabea purcelli

Stefan foto

Lycosidae sp. 10

Lycosidae sp. 2

Foveosa foveolata

24. MIGIDAE

MIGIDAE

Poecilomigas sp.1

Moggridgea sp. Not *clypiostriata* metatarsi 1 with strong setae

Moggridgea clypiostriata-Migidae

25. MIMETIDAE

MIMETIDAE

Ero sp

Mimetus cornutus Lawrence, 194

Mimetus sp. 2

KEY TO THE GENERA

- 1. Leg I considerably longer >1.5 of leg IV ; tiny rows of spines along the basal margin of at least femur I; also sometimes pro- and retromargin femur II*Mimetus*
- Leg I less than 1.3 times leg IV *Ero*

Ero sp. 1

Mimetus cornutus

Mimetus sp. 2

27. MYSMENIDAE

28. NEMESIIDAE

NEMESIIDAE

- size: 13–30 mm; sexual dimorphism in size and shape
- rastellum absent; fovea short, more or less straight or procurved
- posterior spinnerets long, wide apart
- carapace low and hirsute, with cephalic region slightly arched
- live in silk-lined burrows made under rocks

Key to the Genera of the Savanna Biome

Both males and females with two rows of teeth on paired tarsal claws; endites with strongly produced heel with cuspules scopulae entire on tarsi II of female.....Anaminae *Entypesa*; *Hermacha*; *Lepthercus*
 Males with S-shaped row of teeth on paired claws (fig. 58f) and females with two rows ; endites rectangular without heel but with numerous cuspules; scopulae on tarsi II of female reduced or absent Bemmerinae *Spiroctenus*

1. KEY TO THE SOUTHAFRICA GENERA OF THE ANAMINAE

1. Tarsi I-IV with strong scopulae; preening comb present or absent 2
 -. Tarsi I with thin scopulae, tarsi II-IV with scopulae weak or absent; preening comb present; tarsi of male palp elongate *Entypesa*
2. Metatarsal preening comb present; tibia I of male with one strong spine *Hermacha*
 - Metatarsal preening comb absent; tibia I of male with cuticular spur *Lepthercus*

Entypesa schoutedeni

2738d - Altitudinal, 10_10S, Spiders, Nemesidae, *Entypesa*, *schoutedeni*

2908d - Altitudinal, 06_16S, Spiders, Nemesidae, *Entypesa*, sp.01

Hermacha mazoena

2809e - Altitudinal, 06_16S, Spiders, Nemesidae, *Entypesa*, sp.0

Spiroctenus

Spiroctenus punctatata cf.

Lepthercus

29. NEPHILIDAE

NEPHILIDAE

- *association*: large orb-webs in shrubs and trees
- body size: 4–40 mm, males sexually dimorphic, males much smaller
- three claws; legs sometimes banded and with tufts of hair
- eight eyes in two rows, sometimes on small tubercles
- body elongate decorate with patterns

NEPHILIDAE

Nephila fenestrata Thorell, 1859

Nephila senegalensis (Walckenaer, 1842)

Nephila fenestrata

Nephila senegalensis

30. OECOBIIDAE

OECOBIIDAE

- *association*: retreat-web
- body size: 2–5 mm
- three claws
- six or eight eyes in variable arrangement
- carapace sub-circular, wider than long
- two-segmented anal tubercle with double row of fringed setae

OECOBIIDAE

Uroecobius ecribellatus Kullman & Zimmerman, 1976

Uroecobius ecribellatus

31. OONOPIDAE

Gamasomorpha australis H

OONOPIDAE

Gamasomorpha sp.1 -humicola?

Opopaea sp.??

Opopaea sp

32. ORSOLOBIDAE

ORSOLOBIIDAE

Afrilobus sp.1

Dalk eerder Azanialobus?

33. OXYOPIDAE

Hamataliwa fronticornis

Hamataliwa fronticornis (Lessert, 1927)

Hamataliwa kulczynskii (Lessert, 1915)

Hamataliwa rufocaligata Simon, 1898

Hamataliwa strandi (Lessert, 1923)

Hamataliwa sp. 5

Oxyopes angulitarsus Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes bedoti Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes bothai Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes dumonti Vinson, 1863

Oxyopes hoggi Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes falconeri Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes flavipalpis (Lukas, 1858)

Oxyopes hoggi Lessert, 1915

Oxyopes jacksoni Lessert, 1915F

Oxyopes longispinosus Lawrence, 1938

Oxyopes pallidecoloratus Strand, 1906

Oxyopes russoi Caporiacco, 1940

Oxyopes schenkeli Lessert, 1927 sp. 8

Oxyopes singularis Lessert, 1927

strange eyes

Oxyopes sp. 14 abd patter see kulczynskii

Peucetia crucifera Lawrence, 1927

Peucetia viridis (Blackwall, 1858)

Hamataliwa kulczynskii

Hamataliwa rufocaligata

Hamataliwa strandi

Oxyopes affinis =sp. 3

Oxyopes bedoti

Oxyopes angulitarsis

Oxyopes bothai

Oxyopes dumonti

Oxyopes flavipalpis

Oxyopes jacksoni

Oxyopes falconeri

Oxyopes hoggi

Oxyopes longispinosus

Peucetia crucifera

Oxyopes russoi

Oxyopes pallidecoloratus

Peucetia transvaalica

Oxyopes schenkeli = sp. 8

Peucetia viridis (

Peucetia striata

34. PALPIMANIDAE

PALPIMANIDAE

- association: free-living ground-dwellers, often found under rocks
- body size: 3–11 mm
- two claws
- eight eyes

- Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*
- Palpimanus subarmatus* Lawrence, 1947
- Palpimanus squamata*(Lawrence, 1935)
- Palpimanus transvaalicus*
- Palpimanus sp. 2* [epigynum extend v]

Palpimanus armatus Pocock, 1898

Patella longer than tibiae
Epigynum extend past

Palpimanus sp. 2

Diaphorocellus biplagiatus

Palpimanus subarmatus

Patella not longer than tibiae
Epigynum not extend past groove
rounded
Leg I cluster setae; leg II cluster
setae tip metatarsus

Palpimanus squamata(Lawrence, 1935)

Fig. 3. *Ikuma squamata* n.gen. et sp. ♀. Epigastric region.

Palpimanus transvaalicus

Carapace strongly convex

35. PENESTOMIDAE

PENESTOMIDAE

- *association*: retreat-web
- body size: 4–6 mm long
- three claws
- eight eyes in two rows
- dorsoventrally flattened with short legs
- cribellum divided
- abdomen covered with mixture of fine black and broad white setae

PENESTOMIDAE

Penestomus kruger

2289d Gnaphosidae, Altitudinal, sp 01, 06_18S, Spiders

2289pv Gnaphosidae, Altitudinal, sp 01, 06_18S, Spiders

FIRST MALE OF SPECIES

36. PHILODROMIDAE

PHILODROMIDAE

- association: free-living on vegetation
- body size: 3–8 mm
- two claws with claw tufts and scopulae
- eight eyes in two rows
- abdomen variable, heart-shaped, oval, diamond-shaped or elongate

Hirriusa

Hirriusa arenacea (Lawrence,

PHILODROMIDAE

Gephyrota glouca

Hirriusa bidentata

Hirriusa variegata (Simon, 1895)

Philodromus browningi Lawrence, 1952

Philodromus guineensis Millot, 1941

Suemus punctatus Lawrence, 1938

Tibellus australis (Simon, 1910)

Tibellus minor Lessert, 1919

Tibellus sunetae Van den Berg & Dippenaar-
new genus

Hirriusa bidentata

Hirriusa variegata

Philodromus browningi

Philodromus guineensis

Gephyrota glouca

Philodromus grosi Lessert,

Philodromus sp. 1 ebo?

PHILODROMIDAE CONT.

Tibellus australis

Tibellus minor

Tibellus sunetae

new genus

Suemus punctatus

PHILODROMIDAE *Philodromus* sp. 1 LAJUMA 1632

Thanatus dorsilineatus

38. PHOLCIDAE

PHOLCIDAE

- association: space-web
- body size: 2–10 mm
- three claws
- six or eight eyes, usually single pair and two triads
- very long fine legs
- abdomen cylindrical, globose or triangular
- egg sac carried in chelicerae

PHOLCIDAE

Micropholcus sp.

Pholcus ciliatus Lawrence, 1938 = *quamtana*

Huber, 2003t

Quamtana entabeni Huber, 2003

Quamtana lajuma Huber, 2003

Smeringopus natalensis Lawrence, 1947 6 eyes

Spermophora peninsulæ Lawrence, 1964

Micropholcus

Quamtana bonamanzi

Quamtana ciliata

Quamtana entabeni

Quamtana lajuma

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Smeringopus natalensis

Spermophora peninsulæ

39. PHYXELIIDAE

PHYXELIDIDAE

- *association*: retreat-web
- body size: 3–16 mm
- three claws
- eight eyes in two rows
- cribellum present

PHYXELIDIDAE

Vidole sothoana Griswold, 1990

Vidole sothoana

40. PISAURIDAE

PISAURIDAE (in part)

- *association*: sheet-webs or funnel-webs
- body size: 10–25mm
- three claws
- eight eyes in 2:2:2:2 or 4:2:2 arrangement
- carapace longer than wide, narrower in eye region

Afropisaura rothiformis

Chiasmopes lineatus (Pocock, 1898)

Cispius problematicus Blandin, 1978

Euprostenopsis pulchella (Pocock, 1902)

Euprostenopsis vuattouxi Blandin, 1977

Maypacijs roeweri Blandin, 1975

Nilus rossi (Pocock, 1902)

Afropisaura rothiformis

Cispius problematicus

Euprostenopsis pulchella

Euprostenopsis vuattouxi

Maypacijs roeweri

Nilus rossi (Pocock, 1902)

PHRUROLITHIDAE

Orthobula radiata

42. SALTICIDAE

Aelurillus sp.1

Baryphas ahenus

Asemonea serrata ???

Brancus bevisi Lessert, 1925 = *B. muticus*

Cosmophasis australis

Bianor

Cyrba lineata

Cyrba nigrimana

Dendryphantes sp

Evarcha culicivora

Evarcha ignea

Evarcha prosimilis

Festucula sp.

Habrocestum albimanum

Heliophanus debilis

Heliophanus lesserti

Heliophanus orchestra

Heliophanus trepidus

Holcolaetis zuluensis

Hyllus argyrotoxus

Hyllus dotatus (

Hyllus treleaveni

Langona bisecta

Langelurillus sp. 1

Langelurillus sp. 2

Langona hirsuta

Massagris sp.

Menemerus eburnensis

Menemerus cf. minshallae

Menemerus zimbabwensis

Myrmarachne ichneumon

Myrmarachne marshalli

Natta horizontalis Karsch

Pachyballus transversus

Pellenes epularis

Pellenes tharinae

Phintella

Phlegra cf. procera

Phlegra cf. varia

Phlegra nuda

Phlegra certa

Portia schultzi

Pignus simoni

Pellenes bulawayoensis

Pseudicius (nuclearis-group)

Rhene machadoi

Icius insolidus (Wesolowska, 1999)

Stenaelurillus guttiger

Stenaelurillus natalensis

Thyene coccineovittata

Thyene dakarensis

Thyene inflata

Thyene ogdeni

Thyene natalii

Thyene semiargentea

Thyene thyenioides

Thyenula aurantiaca

Thyenula oranjensis

Thyenula sempiterna

Tomomingi szuetsi

Tusitala barbata

SALTICIDAE white bands

© Vida van der Wall

Tanzania minutus
(Wesolowska & Russell-Smith,

VERY SMALL

SCYTODIDAE

Scytodes clavata Benoit, 1965

Scytodes fusca Walckenaer, 1837

Scytodes maritima Lawrence, 1938

Scytodes cf. quinqu Lawrence, 1927

Scytodes clavata

Scytodes fusca

Scytodes maritima

Scytodes quinqu

SEGESTRIIDAE

Ariadna sp.1 umtalica?

SELENOPIDAE

Anyphops spenceri

Anyphos barbertonensis (Lawrence, 1940)

Selenops brachycephalus Lawrence, 1940

Selenops tenebrosus Lawrence, 1940

Selenops zuluanus Lawrence, 1940

Selenops brachycephalus

Selenops tenebrosus

Anyphops spenceri

Selenops zuluanus

Anyphops sp. 1

Anyphops barnardi (

SICARIIDAE

Loxosceles simillima

Loxosceles spiniceps Lawrence, 1952 NOT THERE

Sicarius spiniceps = *hahnii*?

Loxosceles simillima

Sicarius hahnii

SPARASSIDAE

Eusparassus borakalalo

Palystes superciliosus

Olios chubbi

Pseudomicrommata longipes

FIG. 65. *Olios correvoeni* choupangensis n. subsp. ♂

Olios correvoeni

Olios sjostedti Lessert, 1921

Palystes johnstoni

Palystes leroyorum Croeser, 1996

TETRAGNATHIDAE

Diphya simoni

Leucauge festiva (Blackwall, 1866)

Leucauge levanderi (Kulczynski, 1901)

Leucauge thomeensis Kraus, 1960

Meta sp. 1

Tetragnatha boydi O.P.-Cambridge, 1898

Tetragnatha subsquamata Okuma, 1985

Leucauge levanderi

Diphya simoni

Leucauge thomeensis

Leucauge decorata (

Leucauge festiva

Meta sp. 1

Tetragnatha boydi

Tetragnatha subsquamata

THERAPHOSIDAE

Ceratogyrus bechuanicus Purcell, 1902

Ceratogyrus darlingi Pocock, 1897

Harpactirella flavipilosa Lawrence, 1936

Augacephalus junodi

Harpactirella overdijki

Augacephalus junodi

Ceratogyrus darlingi

Ceratogyrus bechuanicus

Harpactirella overdijki Gallon, 2010

Harpactirella flavipilosa = *Pterinochilus*

THERIDIIDAE

Anelosimus nelsoni

Archaearanea sp.1

Argyrodes zonatus

Argyrodes sp. 2

Choriozopella tragardi

Chryso sp.10

Coleosoma

Coscinida sp. 1

Crustulina sp. 1

Dipoenia sp.4

Dipoenura

Episinus bilineatus

Euryopsis funebris

Euryopsis episinoides
(Walckenaer, 1847) sp. 2

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Latrodectus geometricus

Latrodectus renivulvatus

Phoroncidia sp. 1 *eburnea*

Steatoda *capensis*

Steatoda sp. 2

Theridion *purcelli*

Theridion sp. 1

Theridion sp. 2

Theridion sp. 3

Theridion sp. 4

Theridion sp. 5

Theridion sp. 6

Theridion sp. 7

Thymoites sp. 1

Theridiidae sp. 1

Tidarren sp. 1

2375 Altitudinal Spiders

2372cm Altitudinal Spiders

steat0da

THOMISIDAE

Ansiea tuckeri

Diaea puncta

Heriaeus crassispinus

Heriaeus peterwebbi

Misumenops rubrodecoratus

Monaeses austrinus

Mystaria savannensis

Oxytate argenteooculata

Oxytate concolor

Oxytate phaenopomatiformis ??

Oxytate ribes

Pactates compactes

Pherecydes nicolaasi

Runcinia aethiops

Runcinia flavida

Simorcus cotti

Sylligma ndumi

Synema decens

Synema imitator

Synema langheldi

Synema nigrotibiale

Synema vallotoni ???

Thomisops bullatus

Thomisops pupa

Thomisus citrinellus

Thomisus congoensis

Thomisus daradiodes

Thomisus granulatus

Thomisus kalaharinus

Thomisus scrupeus

Thomisus spiculosus

Tmarus africanus

Tmarus cameliformis

Tmarus comellinii

Tmarus planetarius

Tmarus natalensis

Tmarus foliatus Lessert, 1928

Tmarus riccii ???

Xysticus natalensis

Xysticus urbensis

TRACHELIDAE

Afroceso martini (Simon, 1897)

Fuchiba aquilonia Haddad & Lyle, 2008

Fuchibotulus kigelia Haddad & Lyle, 2008

Pronophaea natalica Simon, 1897

Thysanina transversa Lyle & Haddad, 2006

Trachelas scopulifer Simon, 1896

Afroceso martini

Fuchiba aquilonia

Fuchibotulus ki-

Pronophaea natalica Simon, 1897

Thysanina transversa

TROCHANTERIIDAE

Platyoides walteri (Karsch, 1886) ??

2292epi Altitudinal, Spiders,
Trochanteridae, sp.01, 02_10N

2292d Altitudinal, Spiders, Trochanteridae,
sp.01, 02_10N

ULOBORIDAE

Hyptiotes akermani Wiehle, 1964

Miagrammopes brevicaudus O.P.-Cambridge, 1882

Miagrammopes longicaudatus O.P.-Cambridge, 1882

Uloborus lugubris Berland, 1939 ????

Uloborus plumipes Lucas, 1845

Hyptiotes akermani

Uloborus plumipes

Femur of male with one pro-lateral and three dorsal setae; palp without conductor, with broad flat tegular spur serving as embolus guide; 6 mm

Miagrammopes brevicaudus

Miagrammopes longicaudatus

Zosis geniculata

ZODARIIDAE

Australutica africana

Caesetius sp.1

Caesetius sp.2

Capheris decorata Simon, 1904

Chariobas cylindricus Simon, 1893

Cydrela schoemanae Jocqué, 1991

Cyrioctea marken Platnick & Jocqué, 1992 *Australutica africana*

Diores auricular Tucker, 1920

Diores sp.1

Heradida sp. 1

Ranops sp. 1

Mastidiores sp. 1

Psammoduon (undetermined sp.)

Thaumastochilus sp.1

Diores magicus

Diores sp.1 = magicus?

Diores sp.2

Diores auricular Tucker,

Diores triarmatus

Chariobas cylindricus

Ranops sp. 1

Cydrela schoemanae

Cydrela sp. 2

Capheris crassimanus

Capheris decorata

Cydrela sp. 1

Cydrela spinimana

Caesetius bevisi

Caesetius inflatus Jocqué

Cydrela sp. 4

Cydrela schoemanae Jocqué,

Zodariidae sp.08

Cydrela sp. 3

Thaumastochilus sp.1

Mastidiores sp. 1

Heradida

Systemoplacis fagei

Cyrioctea marken Platnick & Jocqué, 1992

Rotundrela sp. 1